

Experimental

General method of preparation of N^1 -(2,4-dianilino-*s*-triazine-6-yl-aminoacetyl)- N^2 -arylureas (2): A solution of N^1 -(2,4-dianilino-*s*-triazine-6-yl)aminoacetyl chloride^{5,6} (0.01 mol) and arylurea (0.02 mol) in dioxane or acetone was refluxed for 3 h on a steam-bath. The gummy mass obtained on pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice was dissolved in acetone and diluted with ice-cold water to yield a solid. The solid was treated with aqueous 2% NaOH and boiled with water to remove the acid impurities and arylurea, respectively, and crystallised from dioxane.

N -(2-Chloro-4-arylamino-*s*-triazine-6-yl)-aspartic acid (3): A solution of L-aspartic acid (0.01 mol) in acetone was added to a solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) in acetone and stirred at 0–5° for 2 h. To the resulting solution containing N -(2,4-dichloro-*s*-triazine-6-yl)aspartic acid, a solution of aromatic amine (0.01 mol) in acetone was added and stirred at 35–45° for 2 h. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised to give 3.

N^1 -(2-Arylamino-4- α,β -dicarboxyethylamino-*s*-triazine-6-yl)- N^2 -*o*-nitrophenylthioureas (4): An equimolar mixture of *o*-nitrophenylthiourea (prepared from *o*-nitroaniline, benzyl chloride and ammonium thiocyanate) and 3 was refluxed in acetone at 80–90° for 3 h. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from DMF to yield 4; $\nu_{\max}$ 870–770 (C_3N_3), 1 740–1 680 (NHCONH), 1 520–1 480 (NHCSNH), 1 700–1 680 (COOH) and 1 430–1 400 cm^{-1} (CH_2COOH).

Physical data of compounds 2 and 4 are given in Table 1. M.ps. are uncorrected. The ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Backmann IR-5 spectrophotometer.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 4*

Sl. no.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$ (1=1)
Compound 2				
1.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	225	75	—
2.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	185	71	—
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	190	73	—
4.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	200	68	—
5.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	170	70	—
6.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	214	76	—
7.	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	210	69	—
8.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	185	74	—
Compound 4				
9.	C ₆ H ₅	275	70	+59.0
10.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	290	73	+61.0
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	350	65	+69.0
12.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	167	78	+56.0
13.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	217	61	+71.0
14.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	206	76	+62.0
15.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	192	70	+53.0
16.	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ COO ₂ H ₄	198	69	+51.0

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Biological activity: The compounds were screened against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by using their ethanol solution.

The maximum zone of inhibition was observed against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in 2 (3.5 and 2.0 mm, respectively). The nitro derivatives were more active than others. The thioureas (4) having *o*-anisyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-chlorophenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl groups in the *s*-triazine ring were most active against *E. coli*; while against *S. aureus*, the *para*-substituted products exhibited higher activity than the *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds.

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Variation of Major Constituents of Essential Oil of the Leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn.

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OCIMUM sanctum Linn. (Family : Labiatae), a sacred basil, is an indigenous (doubtfully) aromatic annual plant well known for its essential oil, and its constituents have wide range pharmaceutical and perfumery uses¹. Available literature indicates^{2–5} that there is a great deal of variation in the composition of essential oil of *O. sanctum* grown in different localities. It has been reported^{6,7} that the reproductive stage of the plant exerts considerable influence on the quantity and quality of the oil. But no detailed chemical investigation has yet been done on the variation of essential oil constituents during the yearly reproductive developmental stages.

The present paper deals with the variation of the amount and the major constituents of the essential oil of the leaves at various stages of growth throughout a year.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF TOTAL ESSENTIAL OIL AND ITS MAJOR CONSTITUENTS FROM THE LEAVES

Constituent Mol%	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May
Eugenol	69.89	40.78	46.14	64.19	63.49	57.79	53.68	49.56	56.65	50.19	46.18
Methyleugenol	24.81	12.08	14.34	16.92	5.19	3.41	6.54	9.95	8.53	7.17	11.35
Caryophyllene	2.96	32.15	24.19	10.55	13.68	18.56	22.32	26.08	22.29	22.61	23.10
Others	2.34	14.99	15.33	8.34	17.64	20.24	17.46	14.41	12.53	20.03	19.37
Total essential oil (g/100 g of fresh leaves)	0.35	0.38	0.52	0.79	0.86	0.97	0.58	0.60	0.65	0.74	0.68

Experimental

Isolation of essential oil from the leaves: Plants were grown in the middle of June and fresh leaves (100 g) were collected on the 15th day of every month from July to May and hydrodistilled in a Cleavanger apparatus for 90 min. The essential oil was collected over ether. After evaporation of ether, the oil was dried over anhydrous $MgSO_4$, weighed and stored at 0° .

Glc analysis of the oil: The essential oil in each case was analysed directly by a programmed column temperature glc run (isothermal at 110° for 3 min, $3^\circ/\text{min}$ upto 140° , 25 min isothermally at 140°) on a 10% SE-30 on Chromosorb WHP glass column ($2\text{ m} \times 1/8''$ i.d.) with flame ionisation detector. The major constituents of the oil were characterised by co-chromatography with the authentic samples of essential oils (Dragoco, West Germany). A Becker (Pakard 419) gas chromatograph was used. The response factor of the components was determined using the standards.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that the essential oil content of leaves (Table 1) gradually increased from the month July (oil content was minimum) to a maximum in December and then decreased in January and again increased upto the month April and fell in May. Hence, essential oil may be commercially isolated from the leaves of *O. sanctum* mainly in the months from October to January under local condition. It is better not to isolate the essential oil from the immature plants from July to September due to the low content of essential oil in scanty leaves during this period. It is also difficult to isolate large amount of essential oil from February to May due to insufficient growth of fresh leaves.

Glc analyses of the essential oils revealed the presence of at least thirteen components in each case, among which only eugenol, methyleugenol and caryophyllene are the major constituents throughout the observation period (almost total life period of the plant) and the amount of remaining constituents (designated as 'Others' in Table 1) is low.

The maximum availability of eugenol and methyleugenol in total essential oil was observed in

July whereas that of caryophyllene was recorded in August. For commercial purpose, however, eugenol, methyleugenol and caryophyllene may be isolated from the essential oil of the leaves of *O. sanctum* collected during October–December, October, and November–January, respectively.

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Evaluation of Olive Fruit (*Olea europaea*) Oil Recently Grown in Jammu and Kashmir State

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OLEA europaea is extensively cultivated in some mediterranean countries. Olive fruit oil is known to have some medicinal properties^{1,2}. India imports the oil from some European countries to fulfill its domestic requirements. Recently, some exotic varieties of olive from Italy and Spain have been introduced in some parts of Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh and Jammu and Kashmir States. Chemical investigations of two varieties, 'Ascotrinia' and 'Ascolina', grown in Jammu region have been carried out for appraising the suitability of their oils.